

Methodology and Research Design of Islamic Education Management

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ABSTRACT

This study is defined that the Islamic education method is where the general steps for conveying material so as to be able a number of presumptions concerning the characteristics of Islam as a supersystem are used to achieve educational objectives. Islamic teaching methods are practical procedures that a teacher takes when conducting class instruction. As a result, the method is a statement of the fundamental presumptions of the Islamic material approach, and the technique is how the method is put into practice. This study used a sort of qualitative research known as a literature study approach, which reads, records, and analyzes a variety of sources, including books, journals, and other literature, as a source of research data. According to the study's findings, Islamic education is the process of assisting someone in growing spiritually and physically in accordance with Islamic principles Muslim character. The process of building or managing Islamic educational institutions that engages Muslim human resources and motivates them to successfully and efficiently accomplish the objectives of Islamic education is what is meant by "management of Islamic education." Consequently, the reach of Islamic education research studies is universal in the sense that it covers all domains and is studied with many sources of study concepts. Models and types of Islamic education research in general are no different from models and types of research in other educational research.

INTRODUCTION

The Islamic education method is where the general steps for conveying material so as to be able a number of presumptions concerning the characteristics of Islam as a supersystem are used to achieve educational objectives. Islamic teaching methods are practical procedures that a teacher takes when conducting class instruction. So the technique is the implementation of the method, while the method is a description of the basic assumptions of the Islamic material approach.

Islamic education research methods consist of two syllables Islamic research and education methods. The Islamic education research method is a scientific way to obtain data or information from the Koran, al-Hadith, and the perspectives of Islamic scholars who study education and experts as they are and not as they should be with specific purposes and uses. Knowing the scope, models and types, and criteria for Islamic education research is a requirement for making a better Islamic education research.

Furthermore, research can be defined as a method of systematic research intended to produce knowledge to address issues (Cooper and Emory, 1995). Suparmoko then claims that research can also be interpreted as an effort that is consciously directed to find out or learn new facts and also as a channel for human curiosity (Suparmoko, 1991).

The essence of the research method is a scientific way to obtain data or information as it is and not as it should be with specific purposes and uses. As a scientific method, the research method has the following characteristics:

1. Assessment of relevant knowledge
2. Formation of the concept and specification of the hypothesis
3. Data collection
4. Organizing and analyzing data in a relevant way
5. Evaluation and learning from research findings/results
6. Dissemination of research information
7. Give an explanation
8. Make predictions
9. Carry out the necessary control activities

LITERATURE REVIEW

Islamic education research methods consist of two syllables Islamic research and education methods. The Islamic education research method is a scientific way to obtain data or information from the Koran, al-Hadith and the opinions of Islamic education scholars and experts as they are and not as they should be with specific purposes and uses. Knowing the scope, models and types, and criteria for Islamic education research is a requirement for making a better Islamic education research.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a type of qualitative research with a literature study approach that uses As a source of research data, several sources like books, journals, and other material are read, recorded, and examined. Literature studies, according to research, include a variety of activities that include techniques for gathering literature data, reading, taking notes, and processing. the research material (Zed, 2014). The following are the steps taken in implementing the literature study method:

The data collection carried out in this study was in the form of document data, both from the Koran, al-Hadith, textbooks, scientific journals, and other relevant document sources. After that, the data is collected by the researcher and then critical analysis is applied so that it can be presented descriptively to produce precise and accurate conclusions. In terms of this literature study approach, the researcher looked for literature or library data in the form of teacher professionalism according to the perspective of the Koran and al hadith (Kartiningrum, 2015).

The following is a picture of the qualitative research design flow quoted from Marshall & Rossman (1989), namely:

Figure 1. Qualitative Research Design Flow (Marshall & Rossman, 1989)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Concept of Methodology Islamic Education Management

Understanding Islamic Education Methodology Methodology originates from the Greek word "methods," which has the two syllables "metha" for through or passing and "hodos" for way or road. A method is a strategy used to accomplish a task.. Methodology is the sciences that are used to obtain the truth using searches in a certain way to find the truth, depending on the reality being studied.

The methods that are commonly known in the world of education until now are the method of lectures, method of discussions, technique of experiments, method of demonstration, the assignment method, the sociodarma method, the group work method, the question and answer method, the project method, the lecture method, the simulation method, the model method, the method field trips and so on. All of these methods can be used based on their respective interests in accordance with the considerations of the materials to be provided as well as the advantages and disadvantages of each. In other words, the selection and use of methods depends on the effectiveness of each. As long as it does not conflict with the principles of Islamic teachings, this method may be used in Islamic education (Bukhori Umar: 180).

Based on a few presumptions regarding Islam's structure as a supersystem, the Islamic education method is a generic approach to presenting content to meet educational goals. When a teacher delivers instruction in a classroom, Islamic education practices are actual concrete procedures. According to Muhammad Athiyah al-Abrasyi, the technique is way to gain understanding in students. Meanwhile, Abd al-Aziz defines the method by means of obtaining information, knowledge, views, habits of thought and love for knowledge, teachers and schools. So the technique is the embodiment of the method, while the method is the elaboration of the basic assumptions of the Islamic material approach.

The Concept of Islamic Education Management

Management comes English is derived from the term management, which meaning doing and management. (Hasan Sadli and John M. Echols: 2010 in Halid, 2022). the word "manage" can be used as a verb, a noun, or a title for those who perform management-related tasks. While the understanding of management according to Sondang Palan Siagian Management is the whole process of cooperation between two or more people based on certain rationalities to achieve predetermined goals.

According to Naquib Al-Attas, education according to Islam is the recognition and acknowledgment that is gradually instilled into humans, about the right place for everything in the order of being so that this leads to the recognition and recognition of the right place of God in that order of being. (Ahmad Tafsir, 2013).

Based on several meanings of Islamic education management, Therefore, it may be said that Islamic education is the process of guiding a person towards spiritual and physical growth according to Islamic guidance on developing a Muslim personality. The process of organizing or managing Islamic educational institutions that engages Muslim human resources and mobilizes them to achieve the objectives of Islamic education effectively and efficiently, as stated in the definition above, is what is meant by the term "Islamic education management."

In addition, the concept of lifelong learning in Islamic education education which means that school education is not the only time for everyone to learn, but only a part of the learning time which will last a lifetime. On the other hand, the concept of lifelong education formulates the principle that education is an ongoing process from infancy to death.

The Scope of Islamic Education Management

Islamic education as a subject offered in public educational institutions from elementary school to tertiary level is included in the study's scope.

A. The institution of official, non-formal, and informal Islamic education. Madrasas, Islamic boarding schools, and universities make up the formal Islamic educational institutions. Mosques, raudhatul athfals, madrasah diniyah, and other non-formal educational institutions make up Islamic educational institutions. Family and environmental education are taught in Islamic educational institutions that are not conventional educational institutions.

B. An Islamic educational framework. This study examines the foundations and goals of Islamic education as well as its practitioners, pupils, atmosphere, curriculum, methodologies, and evaluation.

C. Islamic education in concept and history. Concept studies include research on educational concepts in the Qur'an and Hadith. Historical studies include research on the history of thought and institutional history.

Models and Types Research of Islamic Education Management

Models and Types of Islamic Education Research Models and types studies on Islamic education generally are not different from models and types of research in other educational research. The difference lies only in the object and source of the study.

Research can be divided into two forms, namely research using hypotheses and research not using hypotheses. Research that does not use hypotheses is usually descriptive, philosophical, historical, and evaluation research. Meanwhile, according to the type of data used, the research is divided into qualitative and quantitative research.

Qualitative Research Bogdan and Taylor explain research is a research procedure that produces descriptive data about people through written or spoken words that can be observed (Salim, 2007 in Efendi, 2022). However, Indra Prasetia made a qualitative definition consisting of historical, descriptive, developmental, case and field research, comparative causal, pure or quasi-experimental and follow-up studies. (Indra, 2012: 6).

Qualitative research or often referred to as naturalistic qualitative research, is a type of research that examines and can describe complex and concrete social realities. Naturalistic qualitative research is, thus, research that studies people conducted in a scientific setting and places more emphasis on the description of data obtained through field research. In this study, data were obtained using observation, interviews and utilization of documents. Broadly speaking, qualitative research includes:

- The Varied Methods Approach
- Research Background
- Sources of Data The relevant information for this study was gathered from two sources: primary data and secondary data (Suharsimi, 2006).
- Data gathering Methods and Data Recording Techniques: This study employed the observation method and the interview method for data gathering.
- Data analysis, during which researchers must focus on interview transcripts, field notes from observations, research diaries, major event notes from the field, memos, and researchers' reflections.
- Verifying or Verifying the Validity of Data, wherein in-depth observation is employed as a technique, and triangulation is used to separate the data into three groups, including data triangulation, method triangulation, and source triangulation.
- The stages of research where the research referred to in this study is related to the process of conducting research. As quoted by Moleong, qualitative research can be separated into three phases: the pre-field phase; the field phase; and the field phase including data analysis.

Quantitative Research

A lot of numbers are needed for quantitative research, which starts with data collection and continues through data interpretation and outcome presentation. This study in outline includes:

- a. Definition of Quantitative Research
- b. Quantitative Research Assumptions
- c. Quantitative Research Characteristics
- d. Quantitative Research Procedures

Quantitative research implementation based on pre-planned procedures.

The quantitative research procedure consists of the following activity stages:

- 1) Identification of problems
- 2) Literature study
- 3) Development of a conceptual framework
- 4) Identification and definition of variables, hypotheses, and research questions
- 5) Research design development
- 6) Sampling technique
- 7) Data collection and quantification
- 8) Data analysis
- 9) Interpretation and communication of research results

CONCLUSION

According to the findings of the previous conversation, research on Islamic education methods are two elements of the words research methods and Islamic education. Method means a path traversed to achieve a goal. Meanwhile, The process of structuring or administering Islamic educational institutions is known as management of Islamic education.

The scope of Islamic education research studies is universal in the sense that it covers all domains and is studied with many sources of study concepts. Models and types of Islamic education research in general are no different from models and types of research in other educational research. The difference lies only in the object and source of the study.

Furthermore, Al-Qur'an, As-Sunnah, and Atsaar are the three (three) fundamental tenets of Islamic education administration, along with the relevant Indonesian laws and regulations. The performance of their leaders in managing the teaching and educational staff present in Islamic schools heavily influences the management of Islamic education and the management of Islamic education teachers.

Therefore, research methodology in Islamic education management really needs to be considered, namely as a scientific process to obtain data or information from the Koran, al-Hadith, and experts' interpretations and experts in Islamic education management in accordance with the truth of the facts and not as it should be. specific purposes and uses.

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